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Keywords: Microwaves, Lignin, Vine shoots, Cellulose, Biorefinery

Production and characterization of lignin and cellulose fractions obtained from pretreated vine shoots by microwave assisted alkali treatment

Izaskun Dávila^a, Javier Remón^b, Patricia Gullón^{*a}, Jalel Labidi^a, Vitaliy Budarin^b

^aDepartment of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, 20018 San Sebastián, Spain.

^bGreen Chemistry Centre of Excellence, University of York, Department of Chemistry, Heslington, York, YO10 5DD, UK

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: patricia.gullon@ehu.es (P. Gullón).

Abstract

This work deals with the optimization of the second stage of a biorefinery scheme to separate simultaneously cellulose and lignin from hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots. For this, the suitability of the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification was assessed and optimized through a Box-Wilson experimental design. The optimum conditions (150 °C, 6 wt.% NaOH, 30 min) allowed maximizing the lignin removal (82 wt.%) and minimizing the loss of the cellulose (35 wt.%) present in the pre-treated vine shoots. A thorough characterization of the two fractions obtained at optimum conditions was performed: the cellulose rich solid was analyzed by XRD and FTIR and the lignin was subjected to HPSEC, Py/GC-MS, ¹³C- and ¹H-NMR. This purposed second stage would allow performing an integral biorefinery with low energy requirements and environmentally friendly conditions. This approach aligns with the circular economy and the zero waste production philosophies, promoting the sustainable development.

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1. Introduction

The linear economy model adopted over the past few years for the production of fuels and chemicals is expected to cause the depletion of the reserves of non-renewable fossil resources by 2112 (Liguori and Faraco, 2016). This circumstance has led researchers to develop new strategies

and processes to move from an unsustainable linear economy towards a more efficient and greener circular economy, which could allow a global and sustainable bioeconomy to be established (Mohan et al., 2016). Given this scenario, the use of lignocellulosic wastes as renewable resources for the production of chemicals and energy could both lead to the accomplishment of a circular economy, as well as, it could help towards the development of a sustainable waste management (Liguori and Faraco, 2016).

The development of integral biorefineries for the conversion of biomass into fuels and chemicals might be one of the most important pillars for this new emerging circular economy. This approach permits the fractionation of biomass into its main components, which could be subsequently processed to obtain value-added products. Moreover, the biorefinery approach, would permit to work as a closed-loop system in which the generated wastes are reduced, reused and recycled (3Rs approach) (Liguori and Faraco, 2016), which is in line with the circular economy concept.

The use of winery residues has received much attention throughout the past few years due to the sharp increase of their production and the environmental problems related to their management (Dimou et al., 2015). More specifically, according to the International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV), in 2016 the total world area used for wine production was 7.6 mha (OIV, 2016) and more than 60 million tons of by-products are generated per year worldwide (Teixeira et al., 2014). Among the different winery residues, vine shoots are a promising lignocellulosic feedstock due to their high availability, as around 21 millions of tons are produced worldwide annually (Argun and Onaran, 2015). Their employment as an alternative source to obtain value-added chemicals and/or platform molecules could provide useful solutions to the problems that vineyards are facing (Abbona et al., 2007).

A possible approach to carry out an integral revalorization for the exploitation of the main components of the vine shoots has been proposed in previous works (Dávila et al., 2016, 2017). This proposal considered a hydrothermal treatment to obtain hemicellulosic oligosaccharides, as the first stage of a biorefinery scheme (Dávila et al., 2016) followed by a delignification stage of

the autohydrolyzed solid to yield lignin and a subsequent enzymatic saccharification (Dávila et al. 2017). An important consideration to bear in mind when developing a feasible biorefinery approach is the employment of green and high-energy efficient technologies in order to make the process environmentally friendly. Taking this into account, the valorization scenario described above for the vine shoots was assessed from an environmental perspective using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology (Gullón et al., 2018). The LCA analysis disclosed that the weakest points of this route were the high energy and chemical requirements of the delignification process, which worsen the environmental profile of this strategy. The determined environmental profile could be improved by the intensification of some of the stages included in the biorefinery process. In this respect, the use of microwave heating has recently appeared as a sustainable and energy efficient methodology for biomass valorization. It has been widely recognized as a green method for the extraction of biomolecules from biomass (Yu et al., 2014). Regarding delignification, Tatijarern et al. (2013) and Singh et al. (2017) addressed the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification of Thai mission grass (*Pennisetum polystachyon*) and arecanut husk, respectively, to improve the digestibility of these solids in a plausible subsequent bio-ethanol production process.

However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, although some works on microwave-assisted delignification have been published over the past few years, very little attention has been paid on the characteristics of the lignin fraction solubilized during the microwave-assisted alkaline delignifications. Thus, more research is needed in order to gain useful insights into the physico-chemical properties and potential applications of this fraction. Moreover, scarce literature has been found about the whole fractionation of vine shoots by means of a first hydrothermal treatment followed by a second microwave-assisted alkaline delignification. Given this background, this work addresses a microwave-assisted alkaline delignification treatment of hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots. In particular, the influence of the temperature (50 - 150 °C), reaction time (0 - 1h) and NaOH concentration (0.2 - 6 wt.%) as well as all the possible interactions of these variables on the process have been analyzed in depth. Furthermore, the

microwave-assisted alkaline delignification treatment was optimized to maximize and minimize the lignin and cellulose removal, respectively. The hydrothermally pre-treated solid and the cellulose-rich fraction obtained under the optimum conditions were subjected to plethora of analyses. These include a chemical composition, Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analyses. Furthermore, the alkaline lignin obtained under the optimum conditions was analyzed by FTIR, Pyrolysis-Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and chemical compositional analyses.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Raw material

The vine shoots used in this work were from the grape variety Hondarribi Zuri, supplied by the local winery Aldako Bodega S.L. (Oiartzun, Basque Country, Spain). The vine shoots were air-dried, milled and sieved in order to have a single and homogenized batch with a particle size smaller than 0.4 cm. The chemical characterization of this feedstock is presented elsewhere (Dávila et al., 2017). Briefly, the vine shoots are composed by 33 wt.% of glucan, 27 wt.% of hemicelluloses, 26.7 wt.% of lignin, 2.6 wt.% of ashes and 3.1 wt.% of extractives as it was determined by Dávila et al. (2017).

2.2 Hydrothermal treatment of the vine shoots

The hydrothermal pre-treatment was carried out as it was described by Dávila et al. (2016). Briefly, the pre-treatment was performed under a non-isothermal regimen at 200°C and once the temperature was reached, the reactor was cooled down and the solid and liquid phases were separated by filtration. The liquid phase, referred as “liquor” which contained the solubilized products from the hemicellulosic fraction, was kept for further applications, while the solid phase, i.e. the pre-treated vine shoots, was washed with water and stored at 4 °C.

2.3 Microwave-assisted alkaline delignification of hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots

The microwave-assisted alkaline delignification process was carried out in a CEM-Mars microwave system using a 70 mL PrepPlus® reactor and a fibre optic temperature sensor to control the temperature. The hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots were mixed with a NaOH solution (0.2-6 wt.%) using a liquid-to-solid ratio (LSR) of 10 g/g (oven-dried basis). The experiments were conducted at a temperature between 50 and 150 °C, using reaction times ranging from 0 to 1 h. For all the experiments, a ramping time of 5 min and a power of 400 W were used. After the reaction, the reactor was cooled down to room temperature and it was weighted to determine the gas production. Afterwards, the solid and liquid phases were separated by filtration. The solid and liquid phases were then processed as described by Dávila et al. (2017). Once air-dried the obtained solid phase was quantified and subjected to a moisture analysis.

2.4 Experimental design and data analysis

The microwave-assisted alkaline delignification treatment was evaluated through an experimental design in order to determine the influence of the temperature (50 - 150 °C), reaction time (0 - 1h) and NaOH concentration (0.2 - 6 wt.%) on the delignification process. The conditions used in the experiments and the achieved experimental results are listed in Table 1. The experiments were planned according to a 2 level 3 factor Box-Wilson Central Composite Face Centered (CCF, $\alpha: \pm 1$) design. This is a 2^k factorial design, 2^k indicating the number of runs for the single factorial design and k the number of studied variables or factors. Apart from 4 replicates at the central point to determine the experimental error, 6 additional axial experiments were performed to analyze non-linear effects and interactions. This type of design permits the evaluation of the linear and quadratic effect of each variable together with all the possible interactions between the different operating variables. The results of the experimental design were analyzed by an analysis of variance (ANOVA) working with a confidence interval of 95%. The evolution of the response variables obtained from the ANOVA analysis of all the experiments is represented in the different interaction figures. The relative importance of the operating variables and interactions on the

response variables was calculated by the cause-effect Pareto principle. By means of this principle, the relative influence of the operating variables on the different response variables could be quantified and the higher the Pareto percentage the higher is its influence.

2.5 Response variables and analytical methods

The influence of the temperature, reaction time and NaOH concentration on several response variables was analyzed and discussed in this work. These response variables were: the solid and liquid yields (%), the delignification yield (%), the cellulose loss percentage (%), the average molecular weight (Mw, g/mol) and the polydispersity index (PI) of the alkaline lignin. While the first two response variables were directly estimated after the alkaline delignification treatment (Supplementary Material), for the determination of the other response variables, the cellulose-rich solid and the alkaline lignin were further analyzed as follows.

The delignification yield and the cellulose loss percentage were determined by subjecting the cellulose-rich solids to a quantitative acid hydrolysis (TAPPI T-249-cm-09) in order to determine their chemical composition, following the procedure described by Dávila et al. (2017) (Supplementary Material), all the analyses being carried out in triplicate. The determination of the Mw and PI of the isolated alkaline lignin were determined by High Performance Size Exclusion Chromatography (HPSEC) following the procedure described by Dávila et al. (2017). The results supplied by the HPSEC were only comparative as the calibration was carried out using polystyrene standards with different molecular weights (between 62,500 and 266 g/mol).

2.6 Characterization of the products obtained at the optimum conditions

The cellulose-rich solid obtained under the optimum conditions together with the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots were subjected to the analyses described in the Section 2.5 and to FTIR and XRD analyses. The alkaline lignin obtained under the optimum conditions was subjected to chemical, FTIR, Py-GC/MS and NMR analyses to gain a deeper insight into its structure.

The FTIR analyses of the cellulose-rich solid, hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots and alkaline lignin were conducted using a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer, accumulating 8 scans in a transmission mode with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The spectrum was recorded from a range of 4000-600 cm⁻¹.

A Bruker AXS-D8 Advance diffractometer with a Kristalloflex 760 X-ray generator, which produces focused and monochromatized K α X-rays from a Cu source, was used for the XRD analyses of the cellulose-rich solid and hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots. The scans were recorded in the range of 5-35 2 θ over 10 min with a 40 kV and 40 mA current. The identification of the phases present in the samples was carried out using the EVA evaluation software and the Bruker CDS database. The crystallinity index (CrI) was determined using the peak height or the Segal method. In this method, the crystallinity index is calculated from the height ratio between the height of the maximum interference (I_{200}) and the intensity at 18°, referred as I_{AM} (Eq. 1) (Karimi and Taherzadeh, 2016).

$$CrI = \frac{(I_{200} - I_{AM})}{I_{200}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Regarding the alkaline lignin obtained under optimum conditions, it was chemically characterized by a modification of the procedure reported by Erdocia et al. (2014), which was detailed by Dávila et al. (2017). This fraction was also analyzed by a 5150 Pyroprobe pyrolyzer (CDS Analytical Inc., Oxford, PA) coupled to an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph equipped with an Agilent 5973 mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies Inc.) to determine its chemical structure. The pyrolysis method employed was as follows: a ramp of 20 °C/ms until a temperature of 600 °C (15 s) was reached and the interface was kept at 260 °C (Dávila et al., 2017). The identification of the compounds was carried out by comparing their mass spectra with the ones compiled in the National Institute of Library (NIST) and using the works published by Sequeiros and Labidi (2017) and Nunes et al. (2010). Peak area ratios were calculated for compounds with a peak area ratio higher than 0.4 %. The sum of these peak areas was normalized to determine the relative abundance of the obtained compounds (Chen et al., 2015).

Furthermore, the alkaline lignin was subjected to ^{13}C - and ^1H -NMR analyses to collect more information about its structure. 40 mg of the sample were dissolved in DMSO-d_6 and analyzed by a Bruker Avance 500 MHz NMR spectrometer equipped with a z-gradient BBI probe working at 30 °C. The spectral width used was 25,000 Hz for the ^{13}C -NMR spectrometry.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of the alkaline treatment on the solubilization of the pre-treated vine shoots

Table 1 lists the results obtained during the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification of the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots. The solid and liquid yields varied as follows: 39.81 - 93.81 % and 5.60 - 57.47 %, respectively. The relative influence of the operating variables on these response variables according to the ANOVA analysis and the cause-effect Pareto principle is listed in Table 2. These analyses showed that the operating variables exerted the same relative influence on the solid and liquid yields but with opposite effects; i.e. increases in the solid yield took place along with decreases in the liquid yield and vice versa. In particular, the concentration of NaOH and the temperature were the operating variables exerting the strongest influence on the solid yield as it could be seen in Table 2. Furthermore, the interaction between these two variables (10 % and 11 % for the solid and liquid yields, respectively) and the interaction of the reaction time with the temperature and the NaOH concentration had a significant influence (8%) in the solid and liquid yields. This latter interaction denoted a synergetic effect between the three operating variables. McIntosh and Vancov (2011) also observed their synergetic effect on the solid yield when they subjected wheat straw to a dilute alkaline pre-treatment.

Fig. 1 plots the effect of the operating conditions and the most important interactions detected on the solid and liquid yields during the ANOVA analysis. In particular, Fig. 1a and 1b show the effect of the temperature on the solid yield for the lowest (0.2 wt.%) and the highest (6 wt.%) NaOH concentrations and for the shortest (0 min) and longest (60 min) reaction times used in the experiments, respectively. Figures 1c and 1d illustrate these effects for the liquid yield.

Table 2. Relative influence of the operating variables on the analyzed response variables given by the Pareto percentage.

	R ²	I. Term	A (T)	B (t)	C (wt.% NaOH)	AB	AC	BC	A ²	B ²	C ²	ABC	A ² B	A ² C	AB ²	AC ²	B ² C	BC ²	A ² B ²	
<i>Response variables</i>																				
Solid yield (%)	0.938	69.24	-17.78 (21)	-3.81 (8)	-10.99 (23)	-3.92 (7)	-5.54 (10)	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	9.29 (13)	-4.28 (8)	n.s.	n.s.	9.99 (8)	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	
Liquid yield (%)	0.968	27.92	17.49 (18)	3.55 (7)	9.80 (19)	4.43 (7)	6.69 (11)	n.s.	5.40 (3)	-6.29 (10)	-8.56 (8)	5.01 (8)	n.s.	n.s.	-9.99 (8)	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	
Delignification yield (%)	0.997	42.34	24.34 (16)	6.49 (8)	8.42 (19)	5.51 (6)	8.01 (9)	4.77 (5)	9.20 (2)	-7.94 (8)	-12.69 (8)	5.70 (6)	n.s.	9.01 (4)	-14.38 (7)	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	
Cellulose loss (%)	0.907	28.13	3.59 (12)	n.s.	8.31 (28)	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-10.01 (22)	-13.62 (16)	3.67 (11)	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	9.62 (9)	
Molecular weight (Da)	0.995	11602	20273 (19)	3976 (4)	5731 (10)		3256 (9)	1276 (3)	11616 (0)		2811 (9)	1598 (4)	-3378 (4)	-2897 (3)	-17337 (21)				-16449 (14)	
Polydispersity index	0.987	10.23	11.95 (22)	2.75 (5)	2.21 (11)		2.20 (10)	0.88 (4)	6.46 (1)			0.93 (4)	-2.30 (5)		-9.61 (20)				-8.43 (17)	

n.s: Non significant with 95% confidence

Response: I. Term + coefficient T + coefficient t + coefficient wt.% NaOH + coefficient T · t + coefficient T · wt.% NaOH + coefficient t · wt.% NaOH + coefficient T² + coefficient t² + coefficient wt.% NaOH² + coefficient T · t · wt.% NaOH + coefficient T² · t + coefficient T² · wt.% NaOH + coefficient T · t² + coefficient T · wt.% NaOH² + coefficient t² · wt.% NaOH + coefficient t · wt.% NaOH² + coefficient T² · t²

Numbers in bracket correspond to the Pareto percentage which measures the influence of each interaction on the response variable. Pareto values represent the percentage of the orthogonal estimated total value.

For a 0 min reaction time, the liquid and the solid yields were only influenced by the concentration of NaOH, as the temperature did not exert a significant influence (the Least Significant Difference (LSD) bars overlap). Besides, regardless of the temperature, an increase in the NaOH concentration from 0.2 to 6 wt.% led to a substantial decrease in the solid yield along with an increase in the liquid yield. This was accounted for by the positive catalytic effect of NaOH, which provokes structural changes within the lignocellulosic biomass due to partial delignification, solubilization of the hemicellulosic content and/or swelling of the cellulose (Monte et al., 2018).

Conversely, for a 60 min reaction time, the effect of the temperature depended on the concentration of NaOH. Specifically, for a diluted (0.2 wt.%) NaOH solution, the temperature did not significantly influence the liquid or solid yields. However, an increase in the concentration of NaOH produced a decrease in the solid yield together with an increase in the liquid yield due to the positive catalytic effect of the NaOH on the process, as described above. At elevated temperature and using a long reaction time, the positive catalytic effect of the NaOH was promoted. This, favored the breakage of the ester linkages between hemicelluloses and lignin and the breaking of the ether bonds that binds the lignin inter-units, thus leading to a further degradation of the lignin fraction (Xu et al., 2016). The covalent bonds between the lignin and the cellulose are unknown (Sun et al., 2016), thus, it was not possible to determine how the fractionation of the lignin and cellulose took place. The influence of the temperature on the process was also reported by Yáñez et al. (2009) and Dávila et al. (2017) during the alkaline delignification treatment of hydrothermally pre-treated *Acacia dealbata* and vine shoots, respectively.

3.2. Effect of the alkaline treatment on the solid composition

The chemical composition of the solid phases obtained in the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification treatments is listed in Table 1. This solid phase were largely constituted by lignin

and cellulose in different quantities depending on the efficiency of the delignification treatment. In particular, the lignin content varied from 13.98 to 50.76%, while the cellulose content shifted from 36.33 to 66.87%. These variations on the lignin and cellulose content of the solid phases were translated into changes in the delignification yield and cellulose loss percentage that shifted from 9.33 to 89.18 % and from 0 to 34.45 %, respectively.

The cause-effect Pareto principle (Table 2) revealed that the NaOH concentration exerted the strongest influence on the delignification yield and the cellulose loss percentage (19% and 28%, respectively). The delignification yield was also strongly influenced by the temperature (16%); while the influence of this variable on the cellulose loss percentage was slightly lower (12%). The reaction time had a significant influence on the delignification yield (8%), while the cellulose loss percentage was strongly influenced by the quadratic interaction of the reaction time (22%). Fig. 2 illustrates the effect of the operating conditions and the most important interactions detected during the ANOVA analysis on the delignification yield and cellulose loss percentage. Fig. 2a and 2b plot the effects of the temperature on the delignification yield for the lowest (0.2 wt.%) and the highest (6 wt.%) NaOH concentrations and for the shortest (0 min) and longest (60 min) reaction times, respectively, while Fig. 2c and 2d show these effects for the cellulose loss percentage.

Fig. 2a and 2b showed that the effect of the temperature on the delignification yield strongly depended on the NaOH concentration; this effect was more appreciable when long reaction times were used. In particular, regardless of the temperature or reaction time, an increase in the NaOH concentration from 0.2 to 6 wt.% produced an increase in the delignification yield. When a 0.2 wt.% NaOH solution was used, the delignification yield was not significantly influenced by the reaction time or the temperature. Conversely, when the highest NaOH concentration was used (6 wt.%) the delignification yield was significantly influenced by the temperature and reaction time and two different outcomes were observed. When a short reaction time (0 min) was used, an initial increase in the temperature from 50 to 80 °C led to a small decrease in the delignification yield which was followed by a subsequent increase when the temperature was raised up to 150 °C.

When a high concentration of NaOH was used (6 wt.%), a significant delignification of the material (30%) occurred at very low temperature (50 °C) and short reaction times (0 min) due to the positive effect of NaOH on the biomass delignification. However, increasing the temperature could also promote the repolymerization of the lignin fraction, thus decreasing the delignification yield. This leads to a small decrease in the delignification yield when a very short (0 min) reaction time is used. On the other hand, for a long reaction time (60 min) the delignification yield showed a steady evolution between 50 and 100 °C and then it increased when the temperature was raised up to 150 °C. The steady evolution of the delignification yield could be associated to a trade-off between depolymerization and repolymerization reactions. The synergistic interactions between the temperature and the reaction time were also observed by McIntosh and Vancov (2011) during the delignification of wheat straw. Besides, Karp et al. (2015) observed the positive effect that the NaOH concentration and the temperature had on the delignification of switchgrass, while Cheng et al. (2010) indicated that the alkaline concentration and the reaction time exerted the highest influence on the delignification yield of rice straw when NaOH or CaOH were used.

Apart from the lignin, part of the cellulosic matter of the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots was also removed (Fig. 2c and 2d). The comparison between these Figures revealed that the effect of the temperature and the reaction time on the cellulose loss percentage depended on the concentration of NaOH. Particularly, when a low NaOH concentration (0.2 wt.%) was used, two different developments were observed depending on the reaction time. For a short reaction time (0 min), the cellulose solubilization did not take place to a significant extent at low temperature (50-100 °C). However, a further increase in the temperature up to 150 °C promoted the solubilization of cellulose, thus increasing the cellulose loss. This low cellulose removal could be attributed to the initial reactions that the cellulose could suffer in alkaline media, which involves the solvation of the OH groups by hydroxyl ions (Xu et al., 2016). Conversely, when a long reaction time (60 min) is used, the cellulose loss is not significantly affected by the temperature as a cellulose loss lower than 10% was observed within the whole interval of temperature analyzed in this work (50-150 °C). This suggests that when a low NaOH concentration was used, the

removal of the cellulose content of the original solid was favored at high temperatures and/or long reaction times.

An increase in the NaOH concentration from 0.2 to 6 wt. % led to an increase in the cellulose loss percentage regardless of the temperature or the reaction time. For a short reaction time (0 min), the cellulose loss was quite high (25%) and unaffected by the temperature. An increase in the reaction time when a high NaOH concentration was used (6 wt.%) led to a substantial increase in the cellulose loss between 100 and 150 °C. This increase in the cellulose loss percentage with high NaOH concentration (6 wt.%) and high temperatures might be accounted for by the peeling reactions of the cellulose which were promoted by the high temperature and long residence time (Xu et al., 2016). Under alkaline conditions, the hydroxyl groups in the C2 position in cellulose first get ionized, and then form an epoxy compound, which leads to the break the cellulose linkage bond and the loss of the cellulose (Xu et al., 2016).

3.3. Effect of the alkaline treatment on the features of the alkaline lignin

The effect of the operating conditions on the molecular weight and polydispersity index of the lignin was analyzed by HPSEC. The molecular weight (M_w) and polydispersity index (PI) varied from 4000 to 43493 g/mol and from 4.80 to 28.64, respectively. The relative influence of the temperature, reaction time and NaOH concentration on the molecular weight and polydispersity index according to the ANOVA analysis and the cause-effect Pareto principle is listed in Table 2. The molecular weight and polydispersity index were strongly influenced by the temperature (19% and 22%, respectively) and by the quadratic interaction of the reaction time with the temperature (21% and 20%, respectively). Fig. 3 plots the effect of the operating conditions and the most important interactions observed during the ANOVA analysis. Fig. 3a and 3b plot the effect of the temperature on the molecular weight using different NaOH concentrations (0.2 wt.% and 6 wt.%) at the shortest (0 min) and the longest (60 min) reaction time, respectively. Fig. 3c/d show these effects for the polydispersity index of the recovered lignins.

Fig. 1. Interaction plots between the temperature and the NaOH concentration using different times ($t = 0$ min and $t = 60$ min) for the solid yield (a/b) and the liquid yield (c/d). The least Significant Difference (LSD) bars were calculated for a confidence interval of 95% using 4 replicates ($n = 4$).

Fig. 2. Interaction plots between the temperature and the NaOH concentration using different times ($t = 0$ min and $t = 60$ min) for the delignification yield (a/b) and the cellulose loss percentage (c/d). The least Significant Difference (LSD) bars were calculated for a confidence interval of 95% using 4 replicates ($n = 4$).

For both properties, the effect of the temperature depended on the NaOH concentration and the reaction time. When a short reaction time (0 min) and a low NaOH concentration (0.2 wt.%) were used, the molecular weight nor the polydispersity index were greatly influenced by the temperature. However, an increase in the NaOH concentration up to 6 wt.% modified the effect of the temperature on the Mw and PI, as they increased more sharply with the temperature. The increase observed for the Mw when high NaOH concentrations were used was also reported by Li et al. (2015) during the production of lignin from *Eucalyptus* employing different NaOH concentrations. They suggested that increasing the concentration of NaOH could facilitate the dissolution of relatively large lignin molecules. Besides, She et al. (2010) suggested that the increase in the Mw with the increase in the NaOH concentration could be accounted for by condensation reactions between the solubilized lignin fragments.

Fig. 3. Interaction plots between the temperature and the NaOH concentration using different times ($t=0$ min and $t=60$ min) for the molecular weight of the alkaline lignin (a/b) and the polydispersity index of the alkaline lignin (c/d). The least Significant Difference (LSD) bars were calculated for a confidence interval of 95% using 4 replicates ($n = 4$).

The increase in the reaction time led to a significant increase in the Mw and PI, such variations were more marked when a high NaOH concentration (6 wt.%) was used. The effect of the reaction time also modified the effect of the temperature on the Mw and PI of the alkaline lignin, as when a long reaction time (60 min) was used two different developments were observed depending on the NaOH concentration. On the one hand, at low NaOH concentrations (0.2 wt.%) the Mw and PI showed an initial steady evolution up to 100 °C followed by a progressive decay. On the other hand, when a high NaOH concentration was used the Mw and PI increased substantially up to 120 °C, afterwards the increase in the temperature provoked a decrease in the Mw and a steady evolution of the PI. Two counteracting effects might account for the increases and decreases observed in the Mw of the lignin fraction. On the one hand, an increase in the temperature led to a greater spread of the depolymerization reactions, thus increasing the lignin extracted from the vine shoots and the Mw of this fraction. On the other hand, the decreases observed in the Mw and PI could be the consequence of the substantial extension of degradation reactions that the extracted alkaline lignin could undertake when the delignification conditions are too severe. The increase in the PI is related to the increase in the Mw of the lignin, as large lignin molecules with high Mw are likely to decompose in basic media, producing an alkaline lignin with a heterogeneous molecular weight distribution (Sun et al., 2012).

3.4. Optimization of the alkaline delignification treatment

Optimum conditions were determined using the experimental models developed in this work. These models had a R² value higher than 0.90 (Table 2) and therefore they are suitable for prediction purposes. The optimum operating conditions were sought to not only maximize the lignin removal but also to make the process as environmentally friendly as possible. However, as the solubilization of the cellulosic fraction during the alkaline treatment is unavoidable, the cellulose loss percentage was also minimized for the determination of the optimum conditions. Therefore, optimum conditions were estimated as a result of the compromise between the lignin removal, the cellulose loss percentage and the severity of the operating conditions. A relative

importance (1-5) was given to the operating and response variables under consideration. Table 3 lists the relative importance given to each variable together with the predicted optimum values.

The optimum conditions predicted by the experimental model were 150 °C, 30 min and a NaOH concentration of 6 wt.%. Under such conditions, the optimum predicted values for the lignin removal and cellulose loss percentage were 88.8 % and 26.41 %, respectively. These predictions were experimentally corroborated and non-statistically significant differences (p-value greater than 0.05) were found between the predicted and the experimental values. The cellulose-rich solid obtained at the optimum conditions contained 56.96 ± 0.45 wt.% of cellulose and 21.84 ± 1.33 wt.% of lignin. Considering the composition of the hydrothermally pre-treated solid (51.46 ± 1.50 wt.% lignin, 37.35 ± 0.67 wt.% cellulose and 7.89 wt.% hemicelluloses) and taking into account that during this treatment 42.87 % of the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots was solubilized, the optimum conditions allowed removing 81.81% of the lignin and 34.62% of the cellulose present in the hydrothermally pre-treated solid.

Table 3. Theoretical optimization of the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification treatment: operating variables and response variables. The standard deviation was given considering a confidence interval of 95% using 4 replicates (n = 4).

Variable	Objective	Interval of variation	Relative importance (1-5)	Optimum predicted value
<i>Operating variables</i>				
Temperature (°C)	Minimize	50-150	3	150
Time (min)	Minimize	0-60	3	30
NaOH (wt. %)	Minimize	0.2-6	3	6
<i>Response variables</i>				
Delignification yield (%)	Maximize	0-100	4	88.80 ± 7.75
Cellulose loss (%)	Minimize	0-100	5	26.41 ± 11.14

3.4.1 Characterization of the cellulose-rich solid obtained under the optimum conditions

The cellulose-rich solid obtained under the optimum conditions of the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification treatment and the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots were analyzed by FTIR and XRD. The FTIR analyses (Supplementary Material) permitted the determination of the chemical changes that the microwave-assisted alkaline treatment exerted on the

hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots. The band assignment was performed by taking into account the works carried out by Pereira et al. (2016) and Erdocia et al. (2014).

The wide band observed at 3345 cm^{-1} was attributed to the O-H stretching in aromatic and aliphatic hydroxyl groups. The bands at 2968 and 2931 cm^{-1} corresponded to the C-H stretching (Sun et al., 2009), while the band observed at 2863 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the C-H vibration of methylene groups and/or OCH_3 group. The presence of lignin in both solids was corroborated by the presence of the bands associated to aromatic rings, which were observed at 1611 cm^{-1} and 1516 cm^{-1} , and they corresponded to the typical skeletal and C=C stretching vibrations, respectively. The band observed at 1232 cm^{-1} , which was attributed to the C-O stretching, is characteristic of the lignin and hemicellulosic fractions. The different lignin content of these two solids strongly influences the intensity of these bands. The intensity of the band observed at 1232 cm^{-1} was lower for the delignified solid than for the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots, while the one at 1611 cm^{-1} was not appreciated in the spectrum of the delignified solid, thus indicating the removal of high part of the lignin fraction from the hydrothermally pre-treated solid.

In addition, the FTIR spectra also indicated the presence of cellulose in both solids. The bands observed at 1429 cm^{-1} , 1374 cm^{-1} and 1323 cm^{-1} were attributed to crystalline cellulose. The ones showing at 1159 cm^{-1} and 1036 cm^{-1} were also attributed to cellulose since they corresponded to the antisymmetric bridge stretching of the C-O-C groups (Liu et al. 2006) and to the C-O stretching, respectively. These bands could also be associated to hemicelluloses; however, the contribution of the hemicelluloses to these bands might be negligible due to the composition of the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots and delignified solid. The bands observed at 1114 cm^{-1} and 1059 cm^{-1} corresponded to the γ ring in plane vibration (Oh et al., 2005) and to the linkages present in the cellulose, respectively. The intensity of these bands was higher for the delignified solid due to the cellulose enrichment occurring during the delignification treatment, despite of the unavoidable cellulose loss that also took place. The cellulose enrichment of this solid was also confirmed by the appearance of new bands attributed to the cellulose structure that were not present in the FTIR spectra of the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots. These bands were those

observed at 1205 cm^{-1} and 897 cm^{-1} , which corresponded to the C-O-H in plane bending at C6 in cellulose (Sun et al., 2009) and to the amorphous cellulose, respectively.

The morphology and the conformational changes of the cellulosic fraction were also analyzed by XRD. The crystalline structure of the cellulose is an aspect that could be affected during alkaline delignification treatments and it is very important for the biological conversion of cellulose. These changes were measured by the crystallinity index and it was observed that the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification under optimum conditions provoked an increase in the crystallinity index of the hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots from 43.60 % to 65.29 %. This increase might be accounted for by the removal of the amorphous cellulose, since according to Xu et al. (2016) the highly uniform and crystalline fraction of the cellulose is more resistant under alkaline conditions. However, this increase could also be attributed to the removal of lignin, as Karimi and Taherzadeh (2016) also suggested that in lignocellulosic biomass, the amorphous regions that could contribute to the crystallinity index are not only the amorphous cellulose but also lignin, proteins, hemicelluloses or pectins. Monte et al. (2018) and Binod et al. (2012) also observed an increase in the crystallinity index after the alkaline pre-treatment of rice husk and sugarcane bagasse, respectively.

3.4.2 Characterization of the alkaline lignin obtained under the optimum conditions

The alkaline lignin obtained under the optimum conditions was subjected to an acid hydrolysis in order to determine its chemical composition and its impurities. Based on these results, this lignin presented a high purity, as it contained 94.51 wt.% of lignin (considered as the joint contribution of the Klason lignin 92.96 ± 0.91 wt.% and the acid soluble lignin 1.56 ± 0.23 wt.%), 1.16 ± 0.10 wt.% of glucose and 1.58 ± 0.04 wt.% of xylose. The high purity of the isolated alkaline lignin was a consequence of the hydrothermal pre-treatment to which the vine shoots were subjected to, as in this process the hemicellulosic fraction was efficiently removed (61.5 %) (Dávila et al., 2017). However, the remaining glucose and xylose contents of the lignin could be the consequence of the co-precipitation of the lignin with the solubilized carbohydrates (Alekhina et

al., 2015). Carvalho et al. (2018) also obtained a lignin with a 91.6 wt.% purity from an acid pre-treated coffee (*Coffea Arabica*) husk by an alkaline delignification. This lignin only presented 1.9 wt.% of cellulose and a 0.4 wt.% of hemicelluloses.

The alkaline lignin isolated under the optimum conditions was also subjected to a HPSEC analysis in order to determine its molecular weight distribution, as this property can affect its reactivity and physicochemical characteristics (De Menezes et al., 2017). Fig. 4 plots the molecular weight distribution of the alkaline lignin isolated under optimum conditions. The isolated lignin was made up of several lignin fractions with different molecular weights, ranging from 60,198 to 154 g/mol, which is in good agreement with its high polydispersity index (26.41). Alkaline lignins are likely to present high polydispersity indexes due to the possible breaking-up of high molecular weight lignin fractions in an alkaline media (Sun et al., 2102).

Fig. 4. Molecular weight distribution of the alkaline lignin (AL) isolated during the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification carried out under optimum conditions.

In order to have an overall view of the structure of the isolated alkaline lignin, this fraction was subjected to a FTIR analysis. Due to the low carbohydrate content of the alkaline lignin (3 wt.%), the bands observed in its FTIR spectra (Supplementary Material) were attributed to the lignin

structure. Thus, the band assignment was carried out taking into account the works published by Erdocia et al. (2014) and Santos et al. (2017) about the lignin characterization.

The wide band that could be appreciated at 3345 cm^{-1} corresponded to the O-H stretching vibration of alcohols and phenolic hydroxyl groups. The bands observed at 2931, 2863 and 1462 cm^{-1} corresponded to the C-H stretching vibration in methyl and methylene groups and to the C-H asymmetric vibrations and deformations, respectively. The band observed at 1244 cm^{-1} was accounted for by the C-O asymmetric vibration. Bands associated to the vibration of the characteristic aromatic skeleton of the lignin were also appreciated at 1611, 1516 and 1422 cm^{-1} . The presence of syringyl (S) and guaiacyl (G) units in the isolated alkaline lignin could be guaranteed due to the presence of their characteristic bands in the FTIR spectra. These two species were the main phenylpropanoid units that constituted the structure of the lignin isolated from agricultural residues (Sequeiros and Labidi, 2017). The band appearing at 1324 cm^{-1} was attributed to the S and G_{condensed} ring breathing vibration, while the band observed at 1212 cm^{-1} corresponded to the G ring breathing with the C-C, C-O and C=O stretching. Another two bands associated with the lignin structure are observed at 1112 and 1029 cm^{-1} and they were attributed to the deformation of the C-H bond in the S and G rings, respectively. The bands at 915 cm^{-1} and 828 cm^{-1} corresponded to the C-H out of plane bending vibration in G rings and to the C-H out of plane bending vibration of the C2 and the C6 of the S rings.

The chemical structure of the isolated alkaline lignin produced under the optimum conditions was determined by subjecting it to a pyrolysis and by analyzing the generated products by means of a mass spectrometer (Py-GC/MS). This Py-GC/MS analysis was very useful to gain more insights into the structure of the lignin isolated by the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification process, as it is assumed that in higher or lower degree the pyrolysis products represent the structural units that constitute the core structure of the original macromolecular lignin (Sequeiros and Labidi, 2017). The identified compounds and their percentage are listed in Table 4. The identified lignin derived compounds were classified according to their aromatic structure as: guaiacyl derivatives

(G), syringol derivatives (S), p-coumaryl derivatives (H) and catechol derivatives (C) (Wang et al., 2015).

According to the results presented in Table 4, 49.08% of the identified products had their origin in the pyrolysis of the lignin. The amount of lignin derived compounds determined in the alkaline lignin achieved in this work was similar to the one determined by Chen et al. (2015) for lignins isolated by the Klason procedure from different non-woody residues, such as walnut shell or wheat straw (around 50%). The low amount of lignin derived compounds determined during the pyrolysis of the isolated alkaline lignin might indicate that the lignin obtained under microwave heating had a condensed structure. In fact, the high molecular weight of this lignin also reflects its condensed structure.

The lignin isolated in this work had a higher percentage of guaiacyl derived compounds than syringyl, p-coumaryl and catechol derived compounds. During the Py-GC/MS analysis of this lignin carbohydrate derived compounds were not detected; however, fatty acids, such as palmitic, linoleic and stearic acid were observed. Chen et al. (2015) and Constant et al. (2016) also observed the presence of fatty acids in the lignins obtained from different raw materials using different delignification procedures.

In order to gain a deeper insight into the structure of the alkaline lignin, the lignin isolated under the optimum conditions was also subjected to ^{13}C - and ^1H -NMR analyses. The lignin sample was analyzed without being acetylated, as it has been reported that there are few differences in the results obtained from acetylated and non-acetylated lignins (Constant et al., 2016). The assignment of the signals present in the ^{13}C - and ^1H -NMR spectra was carried out using the works developed by Coral-Medina et al. (2015), Santos et al. (2017), She et al. (2010), and Sun et al. (2012).

The ^{13}C -NMR spectrum (Supplementary Material) showed some of the characteristic bands of the lignin structure. The signal observed at 191.7 ppm corresponded to a carbon of a carbonyl group forming part of a benzaldehyde structure [57]. The signal observed at 175 ppm was

associated with carboxylic groups which could belong to aliphatic COOR group produced during the oxidation of the lignin which could have taken place in the microwave-assisted alkaline treatment. However, this signal could also indicate the presence of proteins, hemicelluloses or ester-linked fatty/hydroxyl acids (Sun et al., 2012).

Table 4. Main compounds obtained after the pyrolysis of the lignin isolated in the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification of hydrothermally pre-treated vine shoots under the optimum conditions.

Compound	Retention time (min)	Origin	Main fragments (m/z)	Area %
Toluene	4.01	-	91,92,65	0.77
Phenol	7.42	H	94,66,65	5.44
2-methyl phenol	8.63	H	108,107,77	1.37
4-methyl phenol	8.96	H	107,108,77	3.98
Guaiacol	9.26	G	109,124,81	6.26
4-methyl guaiacol	11.29	G	138,123,95	6.46
Catechol	11.44	C	110,64,63	2.14
3-methoxy catechol	13.21	C	140,125,97	5.28
4-ethyl guaiacol	13.71	G	137,152,122	3.97
4-methyl catechol	14.17	C	124,123,78	1.26
Syringol	15.97	S	154,139,111,96	7.71
3,4-dimethoxy phenol	16.18	S	154,139,111,151	1.57
Cis-isoeugenol	17.27	G	164,149,77	0.76
Acetovanillone	18.87	G	151,166,123	0.98
Guaiacylacetone	19.63	G	137,180,122	0.70
4-allylsyringol	20.71	S	194,91,119	0.70
Acetosyringone	22.48	S	181,196,153	0.50
Palmitic acid	24.94	-	73,60,55	6.78
Linoleic acid	26.61	-	67,81,95	5.90
Stearic acid	26.86	-	73,284,60	7.95
Total syringyl derivatives		S		10.48
Total guaiacyl derivatives		G		19.13
Total p-coumaryl derivatives		H		10.78
Total catechol derivatives		C		8.68
Lignin derived compounds (%)				49.08

From 150 to 100 ppm the aromatic region of the ¹³C-NMR spectra was observed. At 153 ppm a signal corresponding to the C3 and C5 in etherified syringyl units was noted, while the signal observed at 148.5 ppm corresponded to the C3 and C5 in syringyl units (phenolic) and to the C3 and C5 in guaiacyl units. At 135 ppm a signal corresponding to the C1 in etherified guaiacyl units

was appreciated (Sun et al., 2011). The signal observed at 130 ppm was characteristic of C- α and C- β bonds in the Ar-CH=CH-CH₂OH structure of guaiacyl, syringyl and p-hydroxycoumaryl units. Apart from these signals which are characteristic of the lignin, there were others observed at 120 ppm, 116 ppm, 104 ppm, corresponding to C6 in guaiacyl units, C5 in guaiacyl units and C2 and C6 in syringyl units. The signals observed between 95 and 50 ppm were associated with the oxygenated aliphatic region of the ¹³C-NMR spectrum, the lignin inter-unit linkages being observed in this region. At 86 ppm the signal of the CH- α in syringyl units was appreciated (Sun et al., 2011). According to Erdocia et al. (2014) the signals observed at 80-70 ppm and 70-60 corresponded to the C- α in β -O-4 guaiacyl and syringyl units and C- γ in cinnamyl alcohol units, respectively. The strong signal observed at 56 ppm represented the C in Ar-OCH₃ structures, while the signals observed between 40 and 10 ppm accounted for the aliphatic and propylic side chains and they are a fingerprint of the lignin structure.

In the ¹H-NMR spectra of the isolated alkaline lignin produced under the optimum conditions (Supplementary Material), between 6.5 and 7.5 ppm, a complex multiplet associated to the aromatic protons in syringyl, guaiacyl and p-hydroxyphenyl units and to p-coumarates and ferulates was observed (Sun et al., 2012). The signal observed at 3.75 ppm corresponded to methoxyl protons while the signals observed at 2.5 and 3.45 ppm were associated to the DMSO and to the protons of the water contained in the DMSO, respectively. Below 1.5 ppm signals corresponding to protons in aliphatic and methylene saturated groups were observed while the signal observed at 0.8 ppm corresponded to the protons of the methyl group in aliphatic saturated structures.

4. Conclusions

The optimization of the microwave-assisted alkaline delignification of hydrothermally pre-treated vine-shoots (150 °C, 6 wt.% NaOH, 30 min), allowed removing up to 81.8 wt.% of the lignin initially presented in this solid. Simultaneously a cellulose-rich solid (56.96 wt.% of cellulose and 21.84 wt.% of lignin), and an alkaline lignin fraction (95 wt.% purity) were obtained. The FTIR,

Py/GC-MS and ^{13}C - and ^1H NMR analyses confirmed the high purity and aromaticity of this lignin fraction. This work represents a novel investigation not only for the treatment and management of vine shoots, but also for the fractionation of other type of biomass.

E-supplementary data of this work can be found in online version of the paper.

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